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This is to certify that the research paper entitled "AGEING IN THE SHADOW OF DEVELOPMENT: IMPACTS OF THE LOWER SUKTEL DAM PROJECT ON ELDERLY DISPLACED PERSONS IN ODISHA", authored by "Mr. Ashis Kumar Samal", has been successfully published in ADEJ, Volume – 3, Issue – 2 (April-June 2026).

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